

Name: Sindy Poppitz

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Sources: Shipley, William F., Maidu Grammar, 1964

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I. Segmental Properties

Phonotactic patterns

- In syllable-final position, /h/ is a voiceless, nonvocalic offglide with the same position of articulation as the preceding vowel
- /w/ is a bilabial semivowel with the quality of nonsyllabic [u] before or after /i/ or /y/ and before /u/, but somewhat lowered before or after /e/, /a/ or /o/
→ /w/ never occurs after /u/ in the same syllable
- /j/ is a palatal semivowel with the quality of nonsyllabic [i] before or after /u/ or /y/ and before /i/, but somewhat lowered before or after /e/, /a/ or /o/
→ /j/ never occurs after /i/ in the same syllable
- no V-clusters
- only C-clusters, which occur fortuitously in medial position and across syllable-boundaries
- no restricted C as first member of such clusters
- /c/ and /h/ very rare in syllable-final position
- /c/ a rare phoneme with only 5 occurrences in the total corpus
- affixes beginning with /p'/, /t'/ and /h/ also uncommon
- syllable-initially, /s/ is somewhat fortis
- initially and intervocalically, /m/ and /n/ are rather fortis and fully voiced
- no nonimplosive allophones for /b/ and /d/

Phonological processes

- before a N or a stop, voiceless plain stops are unreleased
→ first member of geminate clusters
- /m/ → [N] before /k/ or /k'/
- in one case: change of the preceding V when the derivational stem formant is derived to k'ulu 'to be orphaned' → k'ulaj 'orphan'
- centralization of the V in unstressed syllables

Default syllable template

- Syllable canons: C`V(C')
 C`V(C')
 CV(C')
→ C': one of the restricted C
→ C: any C

- Mono-, di- and poly-syllabic morphs
- Morphs with V-harmony
- vowel length is nonphonemic: V are very short (less than one mora) in unstressed syllables; V are short (about one mora) in closed syllables with primary or secondary stress; V are long (about one and one-half to two morae) in open syllables with primary or secondary stress

Super heavy syllables

- none

II. Prosodic Properties

Primary Stress, rhythmic patterns and the direction

- Stress falls on an initial heavy syllable (CVC only, as there is no vowel length distinction), otherwise on the second syllable
- large number of stems have lexicalized initial stress (Robbins 1991) to involve an underlying degenerate foot
- only one situation in the language in which primary stress of a delayed-stress verb root occurs on the root itself at the phonemic level: negative suffix {men} → /men/ after C and /n/ ~ /men/ after V; Ñmo.´. menÑ → /món-/ ~ /momén-/

Tone system (system of pitch accent)

- no tone
- suprasegmental phonemes (of pitch, stress and intonation):
 - High pitch; middle pitch; low pitch
 - Slight rise in pitch; slight drop in pitch
 - Relative loudness and tenseness in the following syllable; lenis, syllable-final glottal catch, distinct from [ʔ]

III. Morpho-Syntax

Degree and types of fusion between morpheme boundaries

- 2 categories of root morphemes: (1) roots → one segmental syllable; (2) affixes → only a single morphophoneme
- majority of roots function as stems in major form classes and are multivalent, i.e. any root may function freely in constituency with substantival, verbal, adjectival or adverbial suffixes
- stems are roots or combinations of roots in constituency with nominal, verbal, adjectival or adverbial suffixes; multivalent; tend to be especially complex in inner structure in constituency with verbal elements
- minor form classes: (1) not constructions, but single morphemes or (connectives and question words) frozen combinations of morphemes; (2) lacking internal inflection; (3) defined by external distribution

- the morph $\tilde{N}j\tilde{N}$ with a few stems as a kind of derivational stem formant for making verbs from nouns, verbs from verbs and (in one instance) a noun from a verb → nonproductive process
- two noun-stem types:
 - ((né)) - class: limited to second-member position in certain compounds; relative-terms; inalienably possessed
 - all other stems occurring in noun-constructions: (i) stems identical to root morphemes; (ii) stems which contain more than one morpheme → compounds with 2 roots (see IV.); (iii) stems of unique composition (small number of stems contain various noun roots and other identifiable morphemes, but have one segmental element of unique occurrence); (iv) all noun stems may occur with diminutive morpheme {lbe} (pronominal stems not!), e.g. {/ó} 'rock' + {lbe} → //óbe-/ 'pebble'
- theoretically no limit to the number of possible modifiers in a noun expansion, but never more than four or five
- verb consists maximally of a theme and five inflectional suffixes → considerable variability in the ordering of these elements
- stems which occur in major form-class constructions are multivalent → the terms 'noun stem' and 'verb stem' are structurally indefensible; however, many stems (particularly polymorphemic ones) are commonly found in constituency with the suffixes marking substantives *or* with those marking verbs
- verb themes are the result of the combination of stems with one or more thematic suffixes (six position classes, which are all optional)

Infixation, circumfixation or simulfixation

Reduplication patterns

- compounds with root and distributive morpheme {Rto} = reduplication of the root + to and means 'all around', e.g. {sêw} 'river' → /séwsèwto/ 'rivers all around'
- two derivative forms expressing the notions of 'extremely' (with {r}; partial reduplication of the stem) and 'somewhat' (with {R}, total reduplication of the stem); e.g. {t'ês} 'shortness': $\tilde{N}r\ t'ês\ pe\ Im\tilde{N}$ → /t'et'espem/ 'extremely short'; $\tilde{N}t'ês\ R\ pe\ Im\tilde{N}$ → /t'ést'èspem/ 'somewhat short'
- if the morpheme ends in a V, then {R} = $\tilde{N}hR\tilde{N}$, as with {/ítu} 'sickness': $\tilde{N}/ítu\ hR\ pe\ Im\tilde{N}$ → //ítuhtuhpem/ 'somewhat sick'
- if the morpheme is in the form CVCVC, then {R} = $\tilde{N}r\tilde{N}$ and is infixated after the first V and before the second C, as with {banák} 'brightness': $\tilde{N}ba\dots nák\ pe\ Im\tilde{N}$ → /banánàkpem/ 'somewhat bright'
- no attestation of forms with {R} or {r} for roots of the shape CVCCVC

Clitics and particles

- none

IV. Other Questions

Do unstressed vowels undergo any kind of *reduction*?

- Centralization of V in unstressed syllables:
→(esp.) /y/ and /a/ exhibit unstressed, rapid-speech allophones which approach [ɨ] very closely

Word-word combinations (e.g. compounds, incorporation, complex predicates).

- compound-stems: combinations of two or more roots; most of these roots occur elsewhere as verb stems, noun stems or both, but a few occur only in combinations:
 - stems in which both elements are identifiable and in which the first element is commonly found elsewhere in noun constructions; e.g. ÑpânÑ 'tobacco' + Ñpe.´Ñ 'to eat' → /pánpe.´-/ 'to smoke (tobacco)'
 - stems in which both elements are identifiable and in which the first element is commonly found elsewhere in verb constructions
 - stems in which the first element is unidentifiable, e.g. /bók/ ? + ÑwéjeÑ 'to talk' → bókweje- 'to invoke'
 - compound stems with a disyllabic auxiliary verb as second member
 - compounds which have as first member the morpheme {/y.´.} and as second member one of a restricted class of morphemes all but one of which have a lexical meaning involving motion; in some cases, combinations of more than one second member occur

Bipartite stems

- none

Periphrastic morphology

- compounds with root and verbal AUX, e.g. {jásk'ak} 'skinny' + {no} 'along' → /jásk'akno-/ 'skinny man'
- periphrasis: (i) the Periphrastic Remote Past Punctual → this construction may function as the AUX to any verb theme; (ii) the Periphrastic Subjunctive → only morphemes which occur with the subjunctive endings, the resulting forms are used as AUX, with an uninflected preceding main verb; (iii) periphrasis with an uninflected tactic element; and (iv) the Periphrastic Imperative

Note all of the properties listed by the author describing *pre and post-positions*.

- none